

1984 dry and wet seasons. It also was evaluated with other selected varieties and breeding lines in station, zonal, and national variety trials at four locations 1985-87.

Mean yield was 6.2 t/ha (range 4.3-7.8 t/ha) across the trials and locations (see table). ITA173

outyielded check varieties by 10-88% and ranked first or second in 11 trials.

ITA173 is intermediate in height (105 cm) and has good field resistance to common diseases and insects (*Diopsis* spp.). It matures 2-3 wk earlier (115 d) than Supa and IR8, the varieties most widely grown by small

farm holders and commercial rice farms, respectively. ITA173 also has better cooking and eating quality than IR8. It is recommended to both small farm holders and state-owned commercial rice farms. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils and soil characterization

Relationship between urease activity and some rice soil properties

M. A. Saleque, G. M. Panaullah, M. S. Rahman, and N. I. Bhuiyan, Soil Chemistry Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

Urease activity in soil is an important factor in N fertilizer management for

rice. The speed of hydrolysis and the release of N from urea into soil depends largely on urease activity. Once the N contained in urea is released, it is subjected to physical, chemical, and biological processes that ultimately determine how much N in applied urea will be available to the rice crop.

Determination of urease activity is costly and time-consuming. However,

urease activity is known to be closely related to some soil properties that could give an indirect measure. We studied the relationships between urease activity and some properties of rice soils.

Soil samples (0-20 cm depth) collected from ricefields in different areas of Bangladesh were dried, crushed, and passed through a 2-mm sieve. The soils varied in total N, organic matter, clay content, pH, and CEC (Table 1).

Each soil was analyzed for urease activity. Urease activity varied from 2.70 to 8.06 μg urea hydrolyzed/g soil per h (Table 1). It correlated significantly with total N ($r = 0.63^*$) and clay content ($r = 0.70^*$).

No significant correlation between urease activity and any other soil property was found (Table 2). □

Table 1. Some properties of soils collected from ricefields in 10 locations in Bangladesh and their urease activities.

Location	USPA and taxonomy	Total N (%)	Organic matter (%)	pH	Clay (%)	CEC (meq/100 g)	Urease activity ^a
Thakurgaon	Ustochrepts	0.07	1.25	5.1	15	10	4.75
Bogra	Haplaquepts	0.14	2.29	5.5	37	9	7.81
Ishurdi	Haplaquepts	0.13	1.94	7.5	37	26	8.04
Rajshahi	Albaquepts	0.08	1.04	7.6	23	15	6.45
Satkhira	Haplaquepts	0.15	3.02	7.5	23	37	4.44
Faridpur	Haplaquepts	0.13	1.77	7.3	39	17	8.04
Sonagazi	Fluvaquepts	0.04	1.01	7.3	24	10	2.70
Joydebpur	Paleudults	0.13	2.05	6.2	33	18	8.06
Patuakhali	Haplaquepts	0.12	2.08	5.5	37	19	5.73
Gazipur	Paleudults	0.10	1.87	4.9	28	13	5.04
Range		0.043-0.15	1.01-2.29	4.9-7.6	15.10-38.90	9.2-37.0	2.70-8.06

^a μg hydrolyzed/g soil per h.

Table 2. Correlations and estimated relationships of urease activity (UA) in 10 rice soils with some of soil properties. Bangladesh.

Soil property	Linear equation	r^a
N	UA = 2.33 + 34.2 N	0.63*
Organic matter (OM)	UA = 4.91 + 0.69 OM	0.29 ^{ns}
Clay	UA = 1.24 + 0.16 clay	0.70*
pH	UA = 5.43 + 0.10 pH	0.06 ^{ns}
CEC	UA = 5.82 + 0.02 CEC	0.07 ^{ns}

^a* = significant at the 5% level.

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